

Enterprise scale artificial intelligence achieving value in your organization today.

a

^a Director in PwC's Data Analytics practice, Canada

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Sumeet Pelia is a Director in PwC's Data Analytics practice, leading the advanced analytics competency nationally for Canada. This discussion will focus on leveraging organizations data to drive measurable value driving business capabilities.

2. Aim

To practically integrate advanced algorithms (AI, prediction, classification) into existing business process to provide a basis for large scale expansion of advanced analytic capability.

3. Material and methods

Case Studies:

Approach will be discussed through case studies across the following industries:

- Major airline – using AI for dynamic pricing and marketing cross/up-sell
- Public transit - predicting demand for service at station, day, time detail
- Financial services – personalized marketing based on transaction data
- Public sector – predicting traffic usage of major bridges
- Healthcare – building analytics operating model
- Insurance – AI for risk based inspection of home insurance policies

4. Results

Each case study delivered measurable value (increased sales, margin, clicks on digital ads, retention of customers, decrease of waste), and provided a business basis for expansion of this technology in the enterprise.

January 24, 2018

5. Keywords

AI, Advanced Analytics, Big Data

Author biography

Sumeet Pelia is a Director in PwC's Data Analytics practice, leading the advanced analytics competency. His past experience is focused on using analytics to derive value from organizations data assets. This includes extensive experience in the transit and similar industries. In addition to his analytics expertise, Sumeet is a designated Accountant, with an undergraduate degree in Mathematics from the University of Waterloo.

Highlights:

- Advanced Analytic Model Development / Metrolinx: Led 6 month program to explore and analyze transactional ridership data to determine patterns, for the purpose of future ridership prediction, and other use cases. Led development of machine learning algorithm that accurately predicted demand at specific level of detail.

- Machine Learning/ Digital Customer Experience Transformation Program - Large Fortune 500 US-based Airline Company: Recommended and aligned with senior management on strategy for real-time engagement with customers across mobile, online, and kiosk channels. Led creation of customer profile and contextual data set that would be used for real time decisions.

- Digital Customer Experience Transformation Project– Large US based credit card issuer: Managed advisory, design, and solution development of new mobile experience for a large Fortune 500 Financial Services organization. Solution leverage geo-location, purchase history, and other data points to create relevant offers and servicing messages for customers.